

Analyze Product Stock Based on Consumer Purchasing Patterns

Heru Winarno^{1*}, Maulana Zaidan², Hatami Zain³

Faculty of Industrial Engineering, Serang Raya University

Corresponding Author: Heru Winarno: heruwinarno42@gmail.com

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ABSTRACT

DD Diaper Shop is a shop that sells baby equipment such as pempes, eucalyptus oil, powder, shampoo, soap, telon oil and toothpaste. This shop is located in Mancak, Serang, Banten which was founded in October 2021. Shops that offer various types of products require information to determine which products are most in demand or which are less popular in order to manage product inventory, in this case the shop cannot yet manage inventory. product stock. The aim of this research is to obtain information on optimal procurement and the most popular and least popular products. In this research, the method used is the single exponential smoothing method. Based on the results of this research, we can find out how much the number of Pampers Baby Happy products procured in the following month is 29 pcs.

INTRODUCTION

Developments in the business world, especially amidst free markets and advances in information technology, have intensified competition in various business sectors. Increasing demands from customers are also an important factor in the business environment. Therefore, a smart business strategy is the key to maintaining market share and competing effectively (Rismanto et al., 2019). In this context, managing inventory in the logistics system becomes a crucial aspect. The goal is to carefully manage the availability of production goods to prevent shortages when customers need them. In addition, this management supports maintaining the quantity and quality of goods in accordance with market demand and optimizing the use of capital.

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Based on sales data at the DD Diaper store, there is a problem in providing stock, a store needs to pay attention to product stock so that the number of goods available is not more than what consumers buy because the product will pile up, and vice versa, the store should not have minimal stock so that when consumers want buying goods turns out there are no goods, this can result in an imbalance between capital and income in sales, besides that when the goods run out the shop owner has to provide the goods again, which usually buys products once a month becomes twice a month and this will increase transportation costs to take the goods to the agent.

In the various products offered, there are products that are favorites and other products that are less popular with customers. Therefore, understanding customer preferences for products can help management manage stock inventory more effectively. Suboptimal stock control can result in customer dissatisfaction, which in turn can encourage them to look for alternatives from the company's competitors.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Logistics is a series of activities that include planning, executing and monitoring the movement of goods, services, information and various resources from the starting point to the ending point, with the intention of meeting customer needs efficiently and effectively. The focus is to ensure the smooth running of various activities in the supply chain, so that products or services can be available according to the right schedule, location, cost, and under optimal conditions (Bowersox, DJ, et al., 1999).

Logistics Management Functions According to Prihantono, CR (2012), logistics management involves a series of functions which include:

1. Planning function and determining needs The planning function involves setting targets, guidelines and measurements in the field of logistics.

Determining needs is a detail of planning, where all factors that influence needs must be taken into account. Each stage and step in logistics procurement must be considered proportionally to support work unit efficiency and overall organizational effectiveness.

2. Budgeting function This function involves activities to detail needs on a standard scale of currency and cost amounts.
3. Procurement function The procurement function involves efforts to meet operational needs that have been determined in planning, determining needs and budgeting.
4. Storage and distribution function This function includes receiving, storing and distributing equipment that has been procured through this function process, to then be distributed to the authorized agency.
5. Maintenance function Maintenance is an effort to maximize the useful life of equipment so that the equipment can work satisfactorily and minimize damage costs, efforts or process activities to maintain the technical condition and usability of inventory items.
6. The maintenance elimination function is an effort to maximize the useful life of equipment, so that the equipment can operate properly while minimizing damage costs. This includes efforts to maintain the technical condition and performance of inventory items.
7. Control function Control is the core of logistics management, which involves monitoring and securing the logistics management process. This function includes inventory control and supervision activities as its main elements.

METHODOLOGY

In this research, the data used is DD Diaper store product sales data for 1 year, namely from May 2022 to April 2023. The method used in this research is the Single Exponential Smoothing method.

Single Exponential Smoothing

On this stage, stock forecasting of Pampers Baby Happy products is carried out using single exponential smoothing in the following month, namely May 2023.

1. Determine the forecast value to use the single method exponential smoothing can be solved with the following formula:

$$F_{t+1} = \alpha X_t + (1-\alpha) F_{t-1}$$

Information :

F_{t+1} = Forecast for period t+1

X_t = Real value for period t

α = Indicating weight smoothing constant ($0 < \alpha < 1$)

F_{t-1} = Forecast for period t-1

2. Perform forecasting error testing

After getting the forecast using the single method exponential smoothing, next to calculate the error of the results prediction, namely using a method MAD (Mean Absolute Deviation), MSE (Mean Square Error) and MAPE (Mean Absolute Percentage error). To calculate MAD and MAPE formula is used as following:

$$MAD = (\sum |A - F|) / n$$

$$MSE = \sum(A - F)^2 / n$$

$$MAPE = (\sum |A - F| / A) / n) \times 100\%$$

DISCUSSION

1. Determine the forecast value

To use the single exponential smoothing method, it can be solved using the following formula:

$$F_{t+1} = \alpha X_t + (1-\alpha) F_{t-1}$$

Information :

F_{t+1} = Forecast for period t+1

X_t = Real value for period t

α = Weight indicating smoothing constant ($0 < \alpha < 1$)

F_{t-1} = Forecast for period t-1

Based on the formula above, the forecasting results using single exponential smoothing with alpha (α) 0.3 on the Pampers Baby Happy product are as follows:

Table 3. Forecasting Results

Period	Demand	Forecast
May	35	
June	30	35
July	29	33.5
August	31	32.15
September	33	31,805
October	26	32.1635
November	29	30.3145
December	25	29.9201
January	28	28.4441
February	29	28.3109
March	27	28.5176
April	30	28.0623
May		28.6436

Based on the table above, the forecast for May 2023 for Pampers Baby Happy products is 29 pcs.

2. Perform forecasting error testing

After getting the forecast using the single exponential smoothing method, the next step is to calculate the error from the prediction results using the MAD (Mean Absolute Deviation), MSE (Mean Square Error) and MAPE (Mean Absolute Percentage Error) methods. To calculate MAD and MAPE, the following formula is used:

$$MAD = (\sum |A - F|) / n$$

$$MSE = \sum(A - F)^2 / n$$

$$MAPE = (\sum |A - F| / A) / n \times 100\%$$

Based on the formula above, the calculation to measure the forecasting error for Pampers Baby Happy products can be seen in the table below

Table 4. MAD, MSE, MAPE

Period	Demand	Forecast	Absolute Error	Square Error	Absolute Percentage Error
May	35				
June	30	35	5	25	17%
July	29	33.5	4.5	20.25	16%
August	31	32.15	1.15	1.3225	4%
September	33	31,805	1,195	1.428025	4%
October	26	32.1635	6.1635	37.98873225	24%
November	29	30.3145	1.31445	1.727778803	5%
December	25	29.9201	4.920115	24.20753161	20%
January	28	28.4441	0.4440805	0.19720749	2%
February	29	28.3109	0.68914365	0.47491897	2%
March	27	28.5176	1.517599445	2.303108075	6%
April	30	28.0623	1.937680389	3.754605288	6%
May		28.6436			
MAD	2.62105				
MSE	10.7868				
MAPE	9%				

Based on the analysis of forecasting errors in the table above, it can be seen that forecasting used the single exponential smoothing alpha (α) 0.3

method, for the Pampers Baby Happy product, the forecast results in May 2023 were 29 pcs with a MAD value of 2.8, MSE 11, 71 and MAPE 9%.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the results of calculations and discussions that have been carried out using single exponential smoothing, several conclusions can be drawn as follows:

1. In the product stock analysis based on consumer purchasing patterns using single exponential smoothing based on the results of calculating the forecast value for the Pampers Baby Happy product for May 2023, it is 29 pcs.
2. After testing the forecasting error with MAD, MSE and MAPE, the MAD value was 2.8, MSE 11.71 and MAPE 10%. According to the MAPE assessment criteria table, if you get a value below 10%, it is included in the very good criteria, which means the forecasting results can be used.

SUGGESTION

Based on the results of data analysis and the conclusions made, the author would like to provide the following suggestions:

1. It is best for the shop to be able to manage product stock so that there are no stock empties during consumer purchases and to carry out optimal product procurement to avoid product buildup.
2. Evaluate sales transactions every month in order to find out trends in the most and least sold products.

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